

Grounded Theory Categories (Greenfield model)

- Speed-up development (CAT1)
 - Working overtime to meet deadlines
 - Media coverage generates hype
 - Business success (increased ROI)
 - Have the product used in the market
 - Be able to meet deadlines
 - Demonstrate personal abilities
 - Create disruptive technologies
 - Use of standard/known technologies
 - Past experience with same technology
 - Strong community
 - Easier to hire new developers
 - Availability of documentation
 - Use of well-integrated and simple tools
 - Ticket-based tools to manage stories/features
 - Partial use of online and collaborative tools
 - Offline naive tools (whiteboard, post-it notes, ...)
 - Collaborative version control systems to manage the codebase
 - Automatic tools for collecting/report user feedbacks
 - Automatic tools for deployment on the infrastructure
 - Excess of non-integrated tools overloads the team
 - Externalize complexity to third party solutions
 - Deploy on cloud service infrastructure
 - Use external services (SaaS)
 - When possible adopt COTS
 - Keep a simple and informal workflow
 - Informal and frequent discussion to take quick decisions
- Evolutionary approach (CAT2)
 - Uncertain conditions make long-term planning not viable
 - Changes in technologies
 - Dynamic competition landscape
 - User requests
 - Changes in market
 - Changes in team
 - Find the product/market fit quickly
 - Flexibility and reactivity are the main priorities
 - Build a functioning prototype and iterate on it (Minimum Viable Product)
 - Progressively roll-out to larger number of people
 - Small iterations (release frequently)
 - Validate the product

- Find what is valuable for customers
 - Direct contact and observation of users
 - Automated feedback collection
 - Analysis of product metrics
- Product quality has low priority (CAT3)
 - UX is the only important quality
 - Ease of use (operability)
 - Attractiveness of the UI
 - Smooth user-flow without interruptions
 - Limited number of suitable functionalities
 - Efficiency emerges after using the product
 - Users are fault-tolerant in innovative beta products
 - Product should be reasonably ready-to-scale
- Team is the catalyst of development (CAT4)
 - High-impact of CTO/CEO background
 - Very small and co-located development team
 - Developers have big responsibilities (self-organized)
 - Multi-role and full-stack engineers
 - Engineers are responsible for marketing/sales/development (flat structure)
 - Generalists developers instead of specialists (full-stack)
 - Skilled developers are essential for high speed
 - Team works under constant pressure
 - Limited need of formalities between team-members
 - Positive impact of high co-location
 - Previous working experience
 - Knowing each other before starting the company
 - Access to external expertise (Mentors)
- Accumulated technical debt (CAT5)
 - Minimal Project Management
 - Uncertainty makes formal scheduling pointless
 - Only a final release milestone is viable
 - Keep internal milestones short and informal
 - Project progress status not tracked
 - Naive task assignment mechanism
 - Ticket-based systems to control to-do lists
 - No dedicated person for project management
 - Simplify issue management by integrating it with feature management
 - Informal specification of functionalities
 - Informal definition of business objectives
 - Low-precision list of features to implement initially

- Self-explanatory user stories
 - Features prioritization based on personal experience
- Rough and quick feasibility study
 - Lack of formal Analysis
 - Exploring alternative solutions to mitigate limited knowledge
 - Hard to analyze risks with cutting-edge technologies
 - Learn from competitors' solutions and mistakes
 - Past experience in similar contexts helps assess feasibility
 - Keeping the product as simple as possible
 - Naive estimations based on personal experience
- Lack of architectural design
 - Only high-level mockups and low-precision diagrams
 - Maintaining architecture only when strictly necessary
 - Using modularization and frameworks from day 1
 - CTO's academic background lead to a first attempt of architectural design
 - Describing critical interactions with third-party components only
- Lack of automated testing
 - Automatic and partial testing of critical parts only
 - Let users report non-critical bugs
 - Major bugs emerge by trying the product internally
- Tacit Knowledge
 - No need of recording taken decisions (informal discussions)
 - Only minimal and not updated initial documentation
 - Clear and self-explanatory code (standards)
 - Documentation external to source-code perceived as waste
- Initial growth hinders performance (CAT6)
 - Pay off the accumulated technical debt
 - Fear of changing a product which is working
 - Growing necessity of having a release plan
 - Need of control initial chaos with more structured workflow
 - Partially replace informal communication with traceable systems
 - Introduce very basic metrics for measuring project and team progress
 - Need of re-engineer the product
 - Portion of codes needs to be rewritten
 - Substantial refactoring of the codebase
 - Increase scalability of the product/infrastructure
 - Standardize codebase with well-known frameworks
 - Focus shifts to business concerns
 - Hiring new staff members
 - Company and user size grow

- Open the first public release
- Increasing number of users
- Current team not able to manage increased complexity
- Business event
 - New round of funding
 - Acquisition
 - Competing product released on the market
- Severe Lack of resources (CAT7)
 - Time shortage
 - Limited human resources
 - Limited access to expertise